

D1.1 Guidelines for Support Management

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DELIVERABLE NOT APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

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Disclaimer

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

RDA	Research Data Alliance
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions

Executive Summary

These guidelines consist the main aspects of providing additional direct support for the RDA TIGER supported RDA working groups, such as procedures on providing and resourcing support actions, such as subcontracted services (consultancy), 3rd party support, or adoption grants.

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1. General requirements and principles

These principles are followed in all support mechanisms covered in this deliverable

- 1. The services and support must be necessary for the RDA TIGER project goals.**
- 2. The services and support must follow the rules and guidances set by the RDA TIGER Grant Agreement,** they must also generally follow the best practices of the Annotated Grant Agreement of Horizon Europe.
- 3. The services and support contracts and provision must not be a subject of conflict of interest.** No services are obtained from service providers which could lead to conflict of interest in the RDA TIGER consortium or other related bodies (e.g. Selection Committee).
- 4. All support mechanisms are based on best value for resources, and follow the necessary rules, laws and regulations of use of public funds.** The grant and contracts are not intended to always follow the cheapest option, and the RDA Association retains the option to choose the provider which has best overall value of the service (considering e.g. quality or previous experience aspects) for the offered contracts.
- 5. All support mechanisms are only provided on the period of the RDA TIGER grant** (2023-01-01 to 2025-12-31). No support mechanism can go over this time limit.
- 6. All grants are intended only to support the RDA TIGER supported Working Groups,** directly or indirectly (e.g. by service creation or innovation). The grants can not be used to support other activities or initiatives, and support of e.g. Interest Group activities are currently not possible.
- 7. All grants are required to be approved by the Selection Committee.** The mechanisms of selection are then transparent and open to public, and the support mechanisms. Only exception are the initial test grants and support provided for pilot Working Groups early 2023 (before foundation of the Selection Committee).
- 8. All grants and support mechanisms** (which are not in-kind) **are managed by the Research Data Alliance Association AISBL.** No other partner of the RDA TIGER is involved in the direct management (i.e. contractual relationships) of the grants.
- 9. Processes for granting and maintaining these grants are clearly defined, transparent and auditable.** The overall process of the service provision is clearly documented in the calls and requests for service providers, and the selection processes are transparently documented and communicated.
- 10. The selection of service providers is fair and impartial, taking into account service provided and any specific national laws, and regulations of the European Commission and the Horizon Europe Programme.** The service provision also considers e.g. non-eligible countries list of the Horizon Europe Programme, and does not contract providers from such countries.

2. Support mechanisms and related processes

2.1 Overview of the support mechanisms

The overall grants mechanisms are divided to two major groupings, with total of seven subcategories. These are further explained in the following sections.

- 1) **Grants provided directly** to the Working Group members' benefit. This means the resources of the grants are directly given to the members use. These further divided by internal process used to provide this to
 - a) **reimbursements** against receipts for costs incurred (i.e. the WG members can be reimbursed for their expenses against a specific provided budget if they). These costs use either "*C.1 Travel and Subsistence*" or "*C.3 Other goods, subsistence works and services*" budget lines, depending on the type of service provided.; and
 - b) **direct purchase** of services for the use of the Working Group members, intended for specific event costs, etc. which can be purchased by the RDA Association directly. These costs use either "*C.1 Travel and Subsistence*" or "*C.3 Other goods, subsistence works and services*" budget lines, depending on the type of service provided.
- 2) **Grants provided as in-kind support** for the Working Group members, where the given grant is either provided fully in-kind (using internal project personnel and service resources), or via an intermediary who will provide the service to the WG. These are divided by the process and instrument to following categories
 - a) **In-kind services provided by RDA TIGER project staff.** These services are outside of the scope of this deliverable, and the process for selecting them and definition of these services are provided in the specific work packages. The selection process is defined in the deliverable D6.1. These supporting mechanisms are provided by the partner budget lines (mainly "*A. Personnel costs*").
 - b) **In-kind services provided by external 3rd party.** These are divided to following categories:
 - i) **Services provided via external service contract.** These are services which are necessary to support the Working Group and are **significantly different from the services provided by the RDA TIGER project main activities (facilitation, communications, landscape analysis, etc.)**. Such services are requested by the Working Group, and if accepted by the Selection Committee, the RDA AISBL will then find a service provider and contract them to provide these services. These services are then using the normal service budget of the RDA Association. These support mechanisms use the "*C.3 Other goods, subsistence works and services*" budget line of the project.
 - ii) **Services provided via a subcontracting contract.** These are services provided to support the Working Group activities **which are similar to the RDA TIGER provided services**, but are provided by an external 3rd party (subcontractor). These services are required by the WG, and approved by the Selection Committee, which after the RDA Association will seek and contract the subcontractor (person or a company) to provide the services to the Working Group. These grants use the "*B. Subcontracting*" budget line of the project.
 - iii) **Services provided via a 3rd party contract.** These are specific contracts provided to the outside parties (which can also be members of the Working Group) to provide services, limited development actions, or adoption testing for the WG outputs. These grants are required by the WGs, and approved by the Selection Committee, and after that finalized into a public call, which will have full

and transparent internal evaluation for quality and content of suggested services. The RDA Association will finalize the 3rd party Grant contract with the receiving organization, which details the expected work, quality indicators, deliverable timings, payment modalities and other contractual requirements. The 3rd party grant receiving organization will then provide their service or output to support the Working Group activity. These grants use the “*D.1 Financial support to third parties*” budget line of the proposal.

2.2. Grants provided directly to the Working Group members' benefit

These grants are intended to directly support the WG members in their tasks in the Working Group. They differ from other grants in these mechanisms due to their direct impact and applicability to the individuals participating in the WG work. In these support mechanisms the RDA Association (as the representative of the RDA TIGER project), gives direct services and in some cases currency to support the WG activities. The beneficiaries are the Working Group members directly.

The general purpose of these direct grants is to support the WG activities by providing resources for the group work. Although this can be given for many purposes (and further defined by the Selection Committee in WP6), the two main use cases considered in this document are the following:

- 1) **Travel grants** for WG members to participate in the WG activities, typically joining RDA plenaries. These could include direct travel costs (airline or train tickets, hotel costs, etc.) and costs related to subsistence (meals, drinks);
- 2) **Workshop costs** for WG meetings, such as meeting room costs, Audio-visual equipment rental, catering costs, etc.

Generally these are by nature direct costs, and can be directly obtained by the RDA Association or reimbursed against receipts.

2.2.1 Expected procedure

The expected procedure of these grants follow this order of events

1. The Working Group (or soon-to-be WG) will apply to the support mechanisms online, including aspects which could be part of this instrument. If the WG has been provided a facilitator, they can also apply on behalf of the WG
2. The Selection Board evaluates (potentially with external help) the applications and approves the support request. The Selection Board also sets the budget and any specific rules for this instrument for application (e.g. who can use the travel grant, and how this is determined).
3. The RDA Association (WP1) is informed of this need, and the WP1 will evaluate the available grant amount and inform the WG and the Selection board if this needs re-evaluation.
4. The WP1 will then contact the WG members and inform them on the practicalities of the grant provision (budget, reporting requirements, travel policies, etc). The WP1 will also inform on any specific rules about the grant provision in general (e.g. countries or entities which can not be supported by Horizon Europe funding).
5. The WG will send a note on the need to use the Grant to the WP1, which will then evaluate the resource requirements and applicability of the request. This is done in the case of travel using the Travel Request Form of the RDA Association. The WP1 and the

WG members will agree on the best mechanism of grant provision in writing, either with RDA Association obtaining the services directly (e.g. flight tickets, participation fees), or via the WG members self buying the services and providing necessary receipts and documents.

6. The actual service is provided.
7. The WG beneficiaries will report their costs and short document on the process of the travel and/or workshop to the WP1 after the travel/event. If the costs are properly documented, they follow the relevant policies and practices, and receipts are received, the RDA Association will reimburse any remaining costs.
8. In the case the RDA Association has directly purchased the services directly, the documentation is also needed, and failure to provide such documentation can lead to loss of services in the future or in demand of a re-fund from the beneficiary.
9. The RDA Association will record these costs appropriately and report them as valid direct costs to the Commission in the periodic reporting. The beneficiaries are required to provide additional explanations in the case auditor request, up to the end of 2026.

2.2.2. Specific rules

1. No personnel costs (salaries, side costs, etc) can be ever requested in this kind of grant. Only acceptable costs categories are Services or Travel costs.
2. All costs must be documented by itemized and appropriate receipts. Only costs actually incurred can be covered. No tips or non-documented costs (estimates, plans) are covered.
3. The travel must follow the latest Travel Policy of the RDA Association (ANNEX I for the version available at 2023-04-30). In this case, the "Employee" refers to the traveler from the WG. This means that the WG travelers need to fill travel requests to the RDA Association director, follow the purchase and travel rules (including travel class restrictions), and follow the reporting requirements.
4. Travel costs can only be covered in categories of Travel, Accommodation, Subsistence, and participation fees.
5. Travel costs are paid in Euros, and the cost of any currency exchange are not covered by the RDA Association or the RDA TIGER.
6. WG travel grants can only be provided to persons residing in countries which are not restricted by the Horizon Europe rules at the time of travel.
7. Workshops can only be organized in countries which are not restricted by the Horizon Europe rules at the time of travel.
8. Workshop costs (inc. workshop agenda) must be approved beforehand by the RDA Association in WP1 and must follow the general principles of cost-efficiency, best value for money, and prudent use of public funds. The RDA Association and WP1 can request changes in venue or service providers in the case the costs are extravagant.
9. Catering costs must be reasonable and only cover costs which happen during the meeting itself (coffee, lunch), not any dinners or similar off-hours costs.
10. All costs must follow the RDA TIGER Grant Agreement rules for Purchase costs (6.2.C) and Travel and subsistence rules (6.2.C.1), as well as their clarifications in the Horizon Europe Annotated Grant Agreement¹. Failure to follow these rules can lead to partial or full rejection of reimbursement or demand of a refund from the beneficiary (for pre-paid services).

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

2.3. Grants provided in-kind to the Working Group members' benefit

These grants are intended to indirectly support the WG members in their tasks in the Working Group. In practice, the WG applies for additional support, and the RDA TIGER consortium will provide this support as in-kind service, provided either internally, externally by a service provider, externally via subcontractor, or externally via a 3rd party grantee.

Although this support can be given for many purposes (and further defined by the Selection Committee in WP6), the main use cases considered in this document are the following:

- 1) Core RDA TIGER services (facilitation, landscape analysis, communication, output support), which can be provided either by the project staff of subcontractor. Only subcontractor cases are covered in this Deliverable;
- 2) Other support services requiring expertise or specific tools (e.g. designing and operating a survey, text editing, graphical design, researching a subject);
- 3) Technical development for a proof of concept or similar;
- 4) Testing adoption of WG outputs in a real-world situation.

2.3.1 Expected procedure

The expected procedure of these grants follow this order of events

1. The Working Group (or soon-to-be WG) will apply to the support mechanisms online, including aspects which could be part of this instrument. If the WG has been provided a facilitator, they can also apply on behalf of the WG
2. The Selection Board evaluates (potentially with external help) the applications and approves the support request. The Selection Board also sets the budget and any specific rules for this instrument for application.
3. The RDA Association (WP1) is informed of this need, and the WP1 will evaluate the available grant amount and inform the WG and the Selection Board if this needs re-evaluation. The WP1 will also ensure that the budget category involved is correct one (direct cost / subcontracting / 3rd party support) and readjust the grant together with the Selection Board if needed.
4. The WP1 will then contact the WG members and inform them on the practicalities of the grant provision (e.g. timeline of provision, special requirements of the grant, etc.). The WP1 will also negotiate with the WG members on the specifics of the service required, e.g. special qualities or skills needed by the service provider. The WP1 will also inform on any specific rules about the grant provision in general (e.g. countries or entities which can not be supported by Horizon Europe funding).
5. The WP1 will prepare an internal memo on the specifics of the support needed and the plan to provide this. This memo includes the agreements with the WG members on the special qualities needed.
6. Depending on the support instrument, the WP1 will start the either to seek a contractor/service provider or a subcontractor via normal service provider seeking mechanisms (see below on specific rules on service providers and subcontractors), or go through the process for 3rd party grant open call (see below for specific rules).
7. After finding the provider of the services (service provider, subcontractor or a 3rd party grantee), the RDA Association will create the necessary contracts and requirements for

the service provision with the provider. If the contracts include a prefinancing payment, this is done in this phase.

8. The service is provided to the WG, with optionally in-between service quality indicator follow-up with the WG members and (optionally) the RDA TIGER personnel facilitating the WG.
9. After finishing the service, quality of the provided service is evaluated as agreed in the service contract, and if satisfactory, the service provider is paid as agreed. In the case of quality concerns, the RDA Association will negotiate the appropriate measures with the service provider (reduction of payment, remedial work, etc.).
10. The RDA Association will record these costs appropriately and report them according to their nature to the Commission in the periodic reporting.

2.3.2. Specific rules

General rules

1. The services must follow the appropriate rules of the Horizon Europe Grant Agreements (RDA TIGER grant agreement in particular), including the clarifications and notes in the Annotated Grant Agreement.
2. All service providers (contractors, subcontractors or 3rd party grants) are selected based on the overall best value for money, and following the principles of this instrument (section 1 of this deliverable).

Services provided via external service contractor

1. The definition of the tasks of the service contract is made by RDA Association in collaboration with the WG members, considering availability of service providers and the available budget.
2. Service providers are searched openly and transparently, and all service provision requests are communicated in the RDA website (rd-alliance.org) as well as in the social media.
3. The service provider is selected on the best value for money principle, considering the overall principles of this instrument (section 1 of this deliverable).
4. Contracts to the service provider follow normal commercial contracts, and their payment schedules and quality follow normal commercial practices.
5. All contracts are made between RDA Association and the service provider directly. RDA Association is responsible to communicate with the service provider and communicate any requests for corrections or adjustments in service provision.
6. No member of the RDA TIGER consortium or their affiliated entities can be a service provider in these kinds of contracts.
7. The service must be provided during the RDA TIGER project running time (2023-01-01 to 2025-12-31).

Services provided via external service subcontractor

1. The definition of the tasks of the service contract is made by RDA Association in collaboration with the WG members, considering availability of service providers and the available budget.
2. Subcontractors are searched openly and transparently, and all service provision requests are communicated in the RDA website (rd-alliance.org) as well as in the social media.
3. Subcontractors need to follow the overall rules for subcontractors in the Grant Agreement, including reporting and record keeping obligations.

4. The subcontractor must be selected by the criteria of best value for money and no conflict of interest, also considering the overall principles of this instrument (section 1 of this deliverable).
5. The RDA Association will strive to obtain several offers for the subcontract, and select the most applicable in an open and transparent competition. The RDA Association can ask also external experts (e.g. members of the Selection Committee) to help in this selection.
6. Contracts to the subcontract provider will follow commercial templates, including specific cases required by the Grant Agreement, including general eligibility requirements (used during the action, necessary, linked to action, etc.). Costs must be reasonable and comply with the principle of sound financial management.
7. All contracts are made between RDA Association and the subcontract provider directly. RDA Association is responsible to communicate with the service provider and communicate any requests for corrections or adjustments in service provision.
8. No member of the RDA TIGER consortium, or their affiliated entities can be a service provider in these kinds of contracts.
9. The service must be provided during the RDA TIGER project running time (2023-01-01 to 2025-12-31).

Services provided via external 3rd party via Financial Support to third parties instrument

1. The definition of the tasks of the service contract is made by RDA Association in collaboration with the WG members, considering availability of potential service providers and the available budget. Special care is taken to have open call and potential applicants outside of the WG membership.
2. The call texts must include information on
 - a. The maximum amount per third party;
 - b. Criteria for determining the exact amount of financial support (usually fixed);
 - c. Clear and exhaustive list of the types of activities that qualify for financial support for third parties. This includes the description of the required service to the WG;
 - d. Persons or categories of persons (legal or natural) that can receive it;
 - e. Criteria for the criteria for giving financial support
3. The 3rd party grants calls are further checked and approved by the Selection Committee.
4. The calls are then approved by the Commission (REA) Project Officer, and placed in the EU Grants Portal for at least 2 months.
5. The responses to the call are evaluated by the Selection Committee or experts assigned by them in a transparent manner.
6. The RDA Association will inform the recipients of the 3rd party grant on their success and start the grant negotiation with recipients.
7. The WP1 will inform the non-successful applicants on their review scores and feedback (from WP6). Any complaints is handled by the WP6.
8. The contract with the 3rd party grantee follows the general template set in ANNEX II of this deliverable. The RDA Association is free to negotiate other contracts if needed, although the general clauses should remain similar in nature.
9. The 3rd party contracts follow the similar quality checking mechanisms as service contracts (above), and can include checks quality indicators before payment modalities are completed.
10. The 3rd party grant mechanisms should follow the GA specific annex on this subject (included as ANNEX III in this document).

3. Conclusions

This deliverable described the overall processes and policies regarding support mechanisms provided by the RDA TIGER WP1 in the project. These policies and practices can be amended later in the project as the legal and administrative practices around Horizon Europe and 3rd party grants in particular become better defined.

ANNEX I. TRAVEL POLICY of RDA Association

Work travel policy

RDA Association

Ari Asmi, Association director, 2023-01-02

These rules come to effect immediately and they refer to all travel, regardless of the paying project or if the travel costs are from the association general funds.

Principles

The personnel of the association will only travel physically to meetings if it is the only way to efficiently fulfil the association needs. The overall principles of the work travel are as follows: **Travel must be necessary.** This principle states that the employee and the supervisor will together determine the necessity of the travel, in comparison to the other options to fulfil the same operational requirements of the association. These considerations take into account the immediate and strategic needs of the association (e.g. first time meeting with a key stakeholder or collaborator), commitments (e.g. projects), funding situation, employee commitments (inc. rest times, other travel, holiday periods), and compare them to options which will not require physical travel. In practice, this principle is fulfilled during the travel approval process, when these aspects are considered together by the employee and the supervisor together.

Travel must be safe. This is a major requirement for the travel, and the association will not require unsafe travel from its employees. Risks are difficult to evaluate, but the employee is responsible to report any potential unsafe issues related to travel or travel methods during the travel approval process, or if such happen during the travel or between the approval and start of the travel, immediately to the supervisor. Overall, the association considers these risks holistically, but takes the perceived risks seriously. Additionally, the **association requires that the employees will obtain a valid travel insurance** covering at least immediate health costs in the case of sickness or accident for the work travel, and the costs of this insurance are reimbursed to the employee using normal reimbursement rules. Proof of this insurance can be asked during the travel approval process. Additional insurances can be required (and reimbursed) for special cases, based on the overall risk situation of the travel.

Travel must be cost effective and environmentally sustainable. The travel done by the association is done using cost effective and best value basis, and takes into consideration environmental aspects. Most travel is done using cheapest available method which is reasonable in the context of the purpose, goals, and safety of the work travel. Additional guidance for the economical and ecological travel is in the following sections.

Travel is properly documented and follows accepted protocols. This means that the employee will have suitable travel authorization from the supervisor, obtains necessary receipts or other documents to explain and prove the costs and their justifications. These receipts and documents are provided promptly, and the employee is responsible to provide additional information if required.

Economics of travel, specific rules

Exceptions to basic rules below need to be properly documented and approved, generally prior to travel.

Employee is responsible to find, and if asked, to document the cost effectiveness of the chosen travel methods via screenshots, offers, or similar of the other options for the travel.

- Hotels used should be suitable for business travel, but not extravagant. Economy hotels are preferred, and normal rooms (not suites, or special rooms) should be used in almost all cases. If there are unclarity of the acceptance of a suggested accommodation choice, the employee can discuss with the supervisor on the suitability of the service offered. Employees can use different kinds of hotel reservation services, particularly if they help to choose a cost-effective choice. If there is a specific conference/meeting hotel, it may be chosen as long as it is not too much above the normal hotel pricing in the region.
- Reasonable meal costs are reimbursed against receipts. This includes one breakfast, one lunch and one dinner on each full travel day. The receipts must itemise the cost types, at least in general level (esp. food vs. drinks) – employee should ask for itemised bill if this is not clear. On joint dinners, a common receipt might be the only offered, and in these cases the employee should have a copy (e.g. a picture) of the whole receipt and inform in the travel cost claim which parts here her/his. Dinners can include minor amounts of alcoholic beverages. The restaurants chosen should be reasonable and economical for the region of travel. Non-personnel food or drinks are not reimbursed in the travel claims, unless a prior acceptance from the Director is obtained. This can happen on e.g. association business related lunch meetings, etc.
- Other costs can be reimbursed if they are a) necessary for the travel, b) they can be properly documented. Examples include visa costs, obtaining travel documentation (e.g. new passport), medical checks or vaccinations required for the travel, or similar items.
- Employee should consider their carbon emissions of the travel chosen. For this purpose, the employee should calculate the ICAO CO2 emission calculator (<https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/Carbonoffset/Pages/default.aspx>) for the flights, and add 120g/km for ground travel using car or a motorcycle, 12g/km for ground travel using a train, and 19g/km using sea travel. For other forms of travel, the employee is recommended to seek for average values from the internet. This calculation should be included in the travel request on the field “other information.”

For Travel in Europe

- Travel for shorter distances (e.g. to and from airports or train stations) will generally use public transport, if reasonably available. Exceptions for this include e.g. unreasonable travel times due to time schedules of public transport, extremely early or late travel times (before 7:00 and after 22:00), safety or mobility issues, high amounts of needed luggage needed by the association work related to project, or

similar reasons. If the travel between accommodation and meeting place(s) require additional travel, this should in be done by public transport, if possible. Employee is responsible to find the most cost-effective ticket options for these cases (e.g. weekly tickets).

- - For longer distances, 2nd class train tickets, and economy class airline travel are generally the rule for all travel. Exceptions must be justified and approved before travel.

International (outside-of-Europe) travel

- Travel for shorter distances (e.g. to and from airports or train stations) will generally use public transport, as in the Europe, although special attention can be made for the safety, and the physical effort required (e.g. after a long flight).
- For intercontinental travel Economy Plus or similar higher travel classes are acceptable, business class can only be selected if the costs are extremely close or similar to Economy plus tickets, or if no other options are available. All business class ticket purchases need prior acceptance by the association Director, or they might not be reimbursed at all, or reimbursed only using the cost of lower-class tickets.

Forms and procedure

Before travel

- The employee will communicate the need to travel to the supervisor (usually the Director). She or he will fill the Travel Authorisation Request (a Word Document in the Association Sharepoint drive) and send it to the supervisor by email.

- The supervisor will then accept or deny the request, and ask further details if necessary. If the application is acceptable, she or he will then send the accepted document to the Financial Officer by email, and send a note to the employee.
- The employee will start to book the travel methods, hotels, etc. and if there are unclarities of the class/hotel etc., they will ask the supervisor for clarifications (and keep the email received for the travel claim).
- The Financial Officer will assign the travel claim an unique travel number, record the travel claim in proper storage and include in the Association financial forecast the expected costs.

During travel

- The employee will travel according to the travel plan, and if there are major disruptions or changes (e.g. intercontinental travel is cancelled, sickness etc.), the employee will contact the supervisor and the Financial Officer without delay.
- The employee will collect receipts and documents proving the costs accumulated (e.g. hotel, restaurant receipts), as well as justification documentation for the travel claim (e.g. workshop agenda, etc.).

After travel

- The employee will write a travel claim document (in the Sharepoint), with itemised costs and justifications of each. The document, together with attached receipts, and

justification documents (e.g. meeting agenda) are sent to the Financial Officer. The receipts are delivered in a PDF document, but the employee is responsible to store the

- The financial officer will check that the travel has proper authorisation and followed the expected travel economy rules, and the accepted itinerary. He will also check the receipts and their suitability for proving the costs. He will also make necessary currency conversions, using currency conversion rate of the European Central Bank the date of the expenditure in the receipt. If necessary, he will ask the travelled employee for further clarifications. After approving the correctness of the travel claim from his perspective, the financial officer will collate all parts of the travel claim into a single PDF document, called **travel record**:
 - o The original travel authorisation
 - o Travel claim (inc. justification text and any observations by the Financial Officer)
 - o Cost table (with each cost item separated, with a total)
 - o All travel receipts
 - o CO2 emission calculation for the travel

ANNEX II. 3rd Party contract template

COLLABORATION AGREEMENT

between

- (1) Research Data Alliance Association AISBL, having its registered office at Boulevard Louis Schmidt 24, 1040 Etterbeek, Belgium; and represented by its director, Ari Asmi (hereinafter also referred to as the “**CONTRACTOR**”),

AND:

- (2) **XXX** having its registered office at **XXX**; registered under VAT number **XXX**; and represented by **XXX** ; (hereinafter referred to as the “**ORGANISATION**”).

hereinafter referred to as the “Parties” and each of them being a “Party”.

BACKGROUND

- A. The **CONTRACTOR** has been awarded a grant from the European Commission (the “**Client**”) under the Horizon Europe Programme with Grant Agreement Number XX in respect of a project titled RDA TIGER (the “**Project**”), the terms of which are attached as Part 1 of the Schedule to this Agreement (the “**Head Terms**”).
- B. This Agreement sets out the terms and conditions under which the **CONTRACTOR** will pass on the funds allocated to the **ORGANISATION** under the Head Terms and under which the Parties will collaborate on the work to be conducted on the Project.
- C. The Parties have agreed to enter into this contract (hereinafter the “Contract”), of which the general provisions in Part 1 form an integral part. By signing this Contract, the **ORGANISATION** confirms that it has read, understood, and accepted the Contract as well as Part 1 to 3 (incl. the annexes) and all the obligations and conditions set out therein.

TERMS AND CONDITIONS

It is hereby agreed as follows:

1. The Project shall commence on **XXX** and shall continue until **XXX** unless terminated earlier in accordance with this Agreement. The Parties will co-operate to perform the Project. The tasks to be undertaken by each Party for the Project are those allocated to them in the proposal made to the CONTRACTOR for the Project attached in Part 2 of the Schedule to this Agreement (the “**Proposal**”). The ORGANISATION agrees to perform such tasks with reasonable skill and care within the scope of their funding.
2. The ORGANISATION hereby agrees to comply with the Head Terms in so far as they relate and apply to the ORGANISATION’s involvement in the Project. Additionally, the ORGANISATION agrees not to conduct itself (whether by act or omission) in such a manner that would cause the ORGANISATION to be in breach of its obligations under the Head Terms. On termination or expiry of the Head Terms, this Agreement will automatically immediately terminate.
3. The ORGANISATION remains fully responsible for its own compliance with all applicable laws and regulations. The ORGANISATION must perform the Contract in compliance with its provisions and all legal obligations under applicable EU, the national law of the country where the ORGANISATION is registered as well as Belgian law. The ORGANISATION must do so fully, within the set deadlines and to the highest professional standards. In particular, the ORGANISATION must ensure compliance with applicable national tax and social security law (incl. vat law) before working on the action.
4. The ORGANISATION agrees to provide to the CONTRACTOR promptly on request (and where it is legally able to do so) any information, documentary evidence and records in respect of the Project that the CONTRACTOR may reasonably require from time to time in order to fulfil its reporting obligations under the Head Terms.
5. The maximum liability of a Party under this Agreement shall not exceed EUR **XXX** and shall not, in any case extend to indirect or consequential losses. Nothing in this Agreement limits or excludes any Party’s liability for (a) death or personal injury resulting from negligence; or (b) any fraud or for any sort of other liability which, by law, cannot be limited or excluded.
6. The funding to be provided to the ORGANISATION by the CONTRACTOR in respect of the Project is detailed in the payment schedule contained in Part 3 of the Schedule to this Agreement. The ORGANISATION manages the grant money and coordinates all aspects, and all invoices. The ORGANISATION shall only pass on funds received under the Head Terms. If the Client requires the reimbursement by the CONTRACTOR of any sums paid under the Head Terms, then to the extent that such requirement arises from the acts or

ANNEX II. 3rd Party Contract template

omissions of a Collaborator, such Collaborator agrees to reimburse the CONTRACTOR together with any interest charged thereon by the Client.

7. Subject to the conditions of the Head Terms, any intellectual property, know-how and results created in the course of the Project (“Results”) shall be owned by the Party that generates them. Nothing in this agreement shall affect the ownership of any background intellectual property (being any intellectual property owned or controlled by a Party prior to the commencement of the Project or generated by a Party outside the scope of the Project) used in the implementation of the Project. Each Party grants the other Parties (i) a non-exclusive, non-transferable, non-sub-licensable, royalty-free licence for the duration of the Project to use its background intellectual property used in the implementation of the Project solely to enable the other Parties to carry out their respective part of the Project, and (ii) a non-exclusive, non-transferable, non-sub-licensable, royalty-free licence to use its Results for academic and non-commercial research purposes, including research projects funded by third parties (including commercial entities) provided that those parties gain or claim no rights to such Results.

8. Authorship of any publications of the conclusions of the Project will be decided in accordance with normal academic practice. This does not change confidentiality obligations, incl. GDPR, and obligations to ensure open access availability according to art. 29 of the EC Model Grant Agreement.

9. Each Party shall procure that in carrying out the Project, it will comply with all applicable laws, regulations and statutes, including those relating to anti-bribery and modern slavery. Non-compliance with this clause by a Party shall not be sufficient justification for another Party to not comply with its obligations under this Agreement.

10. Any additional conditions which apply to this Agreement (over and above this Agreement) are set out in Part 1 of the Schedule to this letter.

11. This Agreement shall be regarded as though it were a complementary agreement to the Head Terms. Nothing contained in this Agreement shall be so construed or interpreted in any way as to diminish or alter the rights of the Client as set out in the Head Terms which shall take precedence.

12. This Agreement shall be governed by EU law, supplemented, where necessary, by the laws of Belgium. Any disputes concerning the Contract’s interpretation, application or validity that cannot be settled amicably must be brought before Brussels courts, Belgium.

13. A signed copy of this Agreement delivered by e-mailed portable document format file or other means of electronic transmission shall be deemed to have the same legal effect as delivery of an original signed copy of this Agreement.

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IN WITNESS WHEREOF this Agreement is executed as follows:

for and on behalf of [insert full legal name of the ORGANISATION]

Signed: _____

Name: _____

Dated: _____

for and on behalf of [insert full legal name of the CONTRACTOR]

Signed: _____

Name: _____

Title: _____

Dated: _____

SCHEDULE

Part 1

Head Terms

The funds received by the CONTRACTOR are owned by the Client. The CONTRACTOR is a mere holder and manager of the funds. The ORGANISATION has been selected to carry out the proposed services. The terms in this agreement are to be regarded in addition to Article 15 in the RDA TIGER GA. According to Article 15, the following articles are passed on to the ORGANISATION (see also Annotated Grant Agreement of Horizon Europe Programme):

The general terms and conditions are as following:

General provisions

This Contract sets out the rights and obligations, terms and conditions that apply to the ORGANISATION contracted by the CONTRACTOR to assist RDA TIGER by supporting RDA Working groups as described in the RDA TIGER Grant Agreement (no 101094406). Both Parties agree that this Contract governing the assignment of the ORGANISATION is linked to the contract awarded by the Client to the CONTRACTOR and therefore linked to the continuation of the main contract (Grant Agreement Number 101094406) and subject to the same fate.

The Parties have no rights of recourse in cases where the main contract is not finalised or prematurely terminated for following reasons: (i) if the CONTRACTOR is not commissioned to work on the project to the planned extent, (ii) if the project is not executed at all or only in part due to a decision of the Client, (iii) if the Client requests replacement of the ORGANISATION or (iv) if the ORGANISATION cannot provide services at a timing responding to project requirements. In those circumstances, the CONTRACTOR is entitled to amend the terms of this Contract or cancel it unilaterally. However, in this event any tasks undertaken and/or deliverables submitted to the satisfaction of the Client prior to such a termination of this Contract will be reimbursed in accordance with the terms of this Contract. The Parties expressly agree that the ORGANISATION is not a beneficiary of the Grant Agreement Number 101094406 and will act as an independent, collaborating third party directly engaged by the CONTRACTOR. The CONTRACTOR shall have no authority to issue directives or instructions concerning the conduct of the activities described in Annex I. In consideration of the project being funded by the Client, the ORGANISATION acknowledges to be bound by specific reporting obligations to enable the CONTRACTOR's proper accounting.

Each Party shall treat as confidential any information provided to it by the other Party and designated in writing explicitly as confidential. Except as agreed otherwise in writing, this confidentiality obligation shall continue for a period of five (5) years from the date of termination of this Contract. The receiving Party shall not use confidential information for

ANNEX II. 3rd Party Contract template

other purposes than the execution of this Contract and shall not disclose it to any third party without prior written permission of the disclosing Party.

Termination of the contract

This Contract may be terminated by either Party for good cause only by giving one (1) month written notice of such termination to the other Party. On part of the CONTRACTOR, such good cause constitutes the event that the ORGANISATION violates its obligations expressly foreseen by this Contract. The Parties further agree that premature termination of the contract under the EC grant agreement (Number 101094406) shall be considered a good cause in terms of this clause 2.1. On the part of the ORGANISATION, such good cause constitutes the event that the CONTRACTOR breaches its contractual obligations and does not remedy the breach within time, indicated in the notice.

The CONTRACTOR may terminate the Contract for breach of contractual obligations, this includes events, in which the CONTRACTOR identifies that the ORGANISATION: breached its obligations under the Contract, including the lack of impartial or objective performance of the project because of conflicts of interest (being any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the action is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest); stopped to carry out its business object of this Contract and therefore is not able or willing to continue the project; or is engaged in a bankrupt or receivership process.

The CONTRACTOR will give written notice requiring that such breach to be remedied within 30 days. In case the ORGANISATION has not brought remedies from the notice, the CONTRACTOR may decide to terminate the Contract unilaterally.

Any termination or expiration shall not affect the rights and obligations contained herein which by their nature survive beyond termination or expiry, in particular termination or expiry shall not relieve the ORGANISATION of complying with the obligations which shall survive for a period of five (5) years from such expiration or termination.

Conduct of the activities & Reporting

The ORGANISATION agrees to keep the reports describing the results of the work and to store all documents compiled in pursuance of the activities hereunder throughout the duration of this Contract and for a period of five (5) years thereafter, and agrees to submit, on request, any such documents to the CONTRACTOR and the Client; finance and accounting documents remain unaffected.

The ORGANISATION shall inform the CONTRACTOR of the progress and results of the work performed within the agreed deadlines. Deliverables shall only be submitted after an internal check by the ORGANISATION which is responsible for overall conformity and quality.

ANNEX II. 3rd Party Contract template

Before engaging in a communication activity expected to have a major media impact, the ORGANISATION must inform the CONTRACTOR who must inform the Commission.

The CONTRACTOR reserves the right to perform further quality check(s) and the ultimate approval of the deliverable is dependent on acceptance by the Client of the work performed by the ORGANISATION. Any additional work involved in processing or revising the deliverable following comments by the CONTRACTOR and/or the Client is included in the total fee of XXX Euros as agreed in the payment schedule Part 3.

The ORGANISATION will consent to take part in relevant RDA TIGER communication activities and share bio and photo for this purpose.

As a rule, and in addition to EC Model Grant Agreement art. 29, publications shall be pursued on an openly licensed basis, in accordance with the RDA guidance on this, that outputs are available under open licenses Creative Commons Attribution Only 4.0 license (CC-BY) or the Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Public Domain Waiver (CC0).

The ORGANISATION acknowledges that publications under or in connection with the activities under this Contract must acknowledge the funding by the Client as follows: display the EU emblem and include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101094406 .”

The ORGANISATION will provide a mid-term after half of the project time on progress, activities, and any issues, as agreed by the RDA TIGER team. A final report will be submitted by XXX.

The ORGANISATION shall notify the CONTRACTOR without undue delay of any event likely to affect the conduct and/or implementation of this Contract.

Warranty & Liability

The ORGANISATION shall be solely responsible for its operating expenses and shall alone bear the risks inherent in its business. None of the provisions of this Contract can be interpreted as indicating consent by the Parties to form a partnership or joint venture. The ORGANISATION shall have no power or authority to conclude any contract or make any representation, promise, statement or guarantee on behalf of the CONTRACTOR or to bind the CONTRACTOR in any other way.

In respect of any information or materials supplied by one Party to another under the Project, no warranty or representation of any kind is made, given or implied as to the sufficiency or fitness for purpose nor as to the absence of any infringement of any proprietary rights of third parties.

ANNEX II. 3rd Party Contract template

Therefore, the ORGANISATION shall in all cases be entirely and solely liable for the use to which it puts such information and materials, and no Party granting Rights shall be liable in case of infringement of proprietary rights of a third party resulting from the other Party.

The Client cannot be held liable for any damage caused to the ORGANISATION or to third parties as a consequence of implementing the Contract, including for gross negligence. The Client cannot be held liable for any damage caused by any third parties involved in the action, as a consequence of implementing the Contract.

The ORGANISATION shall have sole responsibility for complying with any legal obligations incumbent on it and in accordance with the conditions in this Contract.

No Party shall be responsible to the other Party for any indirect or consequential loss or similar damage such as, but not limited to, loss of profit, loss of revenue or loss of contracts, provided such damage was not caused by a wilful act or gross negligence.

Each Party is solely liable, under the conditions provided by applicable law, for any loss or damages it causes to third parties, and which arise from or in relation to its performance of this Contract.

The limitation and/or exclusion of liability pursuant to 4.5 herein shall not apply in cases of death or injury or damage to body and/or health.

Nothing in this Contract shall constitute a waiver by the CONTRACTOR of its right to seek recourse from the ORGANISATION for any payment made by or on behalf of the CONTRACTOR under any applicable laws, as a consequence of or in relation to an illness or accident of the CONTRACTOR staff resulting from acts or omissions of the ORGANISATION and its staff.

The ORGANISATION agrees to indemnify and hold harmless the CONTRACTOR from claims of third parties, including EU bodies, which might arise due to the ORGANISATION's performance under this Contract, however only to the extent these claims do not arise due to the negligence or wilful misconduct of the CONTRACTOR.

Checks, Audits, and Investigations

The CONTRACTOR may — during the implementation of the action or afterwards — carry out checks and audits to ascertain compliance with the proper implementation of the tasks (including assessment of supporting documents, deliverables, and reports) under this Contract and whether the ORGANISATION is meeting its obligations. The CONTRACTOR may do so throughout the Contract's validity and up to five (5) years after the last payment is made. The ORGANISATION must provide — within the deadline requested — any information and data in addition to deliverables and reports already submitted. The ORGANISATION must allow access to sites and premises on which the tasks specified in this Contract are performed.

ANNEX II. 3rd Party Contract template

Under Regulation No 2185/96 and Regulation No 883/2013 (and in accordance with their provisions and procedures), the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) may — at any moment during implementation of the Contract or afterwards — carry out investigations including on the spot checks and inspections, to establish whether there has been fraud, corruption or any other illegal activity under the Contract affecting the financial interests of the EU.

Under Article 287 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) and Article 161 of the Financial Regulation No 966/2012, the European Court of Auditors (“ECA”) may — at any moment during implementation of the Contract or afterwards — carry out audits. The ECA has the right of access for the purpose of checks and audits.

Findings in checks, audits or investigations may lead to the reduction or rejection of fees, rejection of claims for allowances and expenses or recovery of undue amounts. Moreover, findings arising from an OLAF investigation may lead to criminal prosecution under national law.

Any recovery from fees, costs, or other sums from the CONTRACTOR, which were paid by the CONTRACTOR to the ORGANISATION, lawfully entitles the CONTRACTOR to claim the same amount from the ORGANISATION by giving a written notice.

Part 2

DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK

Timeline:

Date	Milestone Description	Notes
Start date as agreed in contract (Month 0)	Start of the project	
...	...	
M+X	Final report	

Payment Schedule

The CONTRACTOR shall pay to the ORGANISATION, in consideration of the work carried out under this Agreement the amount detailed in the table below. All sums are inclusive of VAT, if applicable. Payments are twice during the project subject to the approval of the mid- and end-term report, based on the agreed proposed work and timeline in part 2 of this agreement.

The payment shall be made to the ORGANISATION for the performance of their activities according to Part 2 as a lump sum of a maximum of EUR XXX (XXX euros) including VAT (if applicable).

The lump sum will be paid in 2 instalments as follows:

- 1. instalment: 50% of the agree Award (EUR XXX) after approval of the mid-term report
- 2. instalment: 50% of the agree Award (EUR XXX) after the approval of the final report

The ORGANISATION must initiate the by sending their payment request (with the information requested in the template in the annex) to the contracting party via E-Mail and address it to the following persons: XXXX

The payment requests have to be received by the contracting party before the end of the EOSC TIGER project (31 December 2025), otherwise the costs will not be eligible, and the payment cannot be made. The payment requests should be compliant to all national and international law, and it should be submitted via the template form (provided in Annex II). The CONTRACTOR is entitled to reject the whole or any part of such payment request submitted by the RECIPIENT, if any of the eligibility criteria required for the payment are not met. Payments will be made within 30 days after reception of the payment request forms. Payments by the CONTRACTOR are considered to have been carried out on the date when they are debited to its account. In case of early termination of the present Contract, the CONTRACTOR has the right to withdraw from his payment obligations.

The ORGANISATION is responsible for informing the CONTRACTOR immediately in case of events, which prevent completion of the agreed award work. The CONTRACTOR is entitled to recover any payments already paid to the defaulting ORGANISATION.

In case of early termination of the present Contract, the CONTRACTOR has the right to withdraw from his payment obligations. For the avoidance of doubt, if the Contract is terminated not due to the fault of the ORGANISATION, the CONTRACTOR shall pay for the works, which have been performed until the date of termination. The payment shall be made after the evaluation and depending on the quality of the delivered service.

Payments will be made in euros to the following bank account; conversions due to other currencies will be made according to the accounting rules of the CONTRACTOR and based on the official conversion rate of the date of the transfer:

IBAN number:

BIC (SWIFT code):

Name of Bank:

Bank Account holder:

The ORGANISATION will provide together with the signed Collaboration Agreement a certificate that confirms the identity of the accountholder

Horizon Europe Programme

Annex to the Application Form (HE CSA)

Topic:

HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-04

Financial support to third parties

Version 1.0
01 July 2021

A. FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO THIRD PARTIES

For more information on terms and conditions: see Work Programme General Annexes section B and Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement Articles 6.2.D.1 and 9.4

A.2. Objectives and results to be obtained

The objective of the 3rd party financial support in the RDA TIGER proposal is to provide project-supported RDA Working Groups (WGs) potential to receive expert support in their development, harmonisation, and alignment activities. The purpose is to directly support the Working Group objectives, and the results of these third-party activities are intended to be directly supporting the creation and/or quality of the Working group Outputs. As each Working Group is different, and requirements for external support will be defined during the project, the exact objectives and results depend on the individual WG roadmaps.

The calls will be designed, implemented and coordinated under T1.2 (issuing calls, contractual aspects) and in close collaboration with the T6.3 RDA Selection Committee task which will oversee evaluation and short listing of the calls and ensure value for money.

The call text and further details on the will be published in EC's Tender portal as well as being distributed widely via RDA dissemination channels. The calls will adhere to EU standards of transparency, equal treatment, conflict of interest and confidentiality

A.3. Specifications

A.3.1. Maximum amount of financial support for each third party

Each third party can receive maximum of 60000 EUR during the project. The support can also be smaller, depending on the Call. No individual or organization (third party) will be awarded more than 60.000 euro (sixty thousand euro). This limit applies cumulatively across all the RDA Open calls. Explicitly, a third party may apply and be awarded funding in different calls, but only be contracted for a total of 60.000 euro. If the limit is reached, no further contracts can be awarded to that individual or organization (third party).

A.3.2. Criteria for calculating the exact amount of the financial support

The amount of financial support is prepared in the T1.2 according to the WP6 approved WG Support plan for the relevant WG. The amount of the financial support will be calculated using a standard day rate of 500 EUR against the estimated effort required to carry out the work, added with estimated other direct costs (e.g. travel, meeting organisation, etc. dependent on the activity type). Other amounts can be also considered, if well justified by the Work Plan (e.g. due to specific type of expertise sought), in which case the decision of the amount of the grant proposed is decided by the Selection Board.

A.3.3. Types of activities qualified for financial support (closed list)

The activities qualified for this financial support include following kinds of actions:

- Adoption Grants to test or verify WG Outputs (for organisations)

- Landscape or gap analysis on relevant RDA WG topic (for individuals or organisations)
- Survey implementation: requirements gathering, executing survey, results analysis (for individuals or organisations)
- Technical harmonisation: small scale technical development, small IT services creation (for individuals or organisations)
- Report writing, editing, and formalisation of results (for individuals or organisations)

Eligible costs include: personnel effort and work time, travel costs, workshop facilitation (room hire, venue facilities, workshop facilitation etc). Awards will be given as lump sums, individual receipts and RDA-supplied timesheets will be requested. All grant awards require reporting of the results and success of the grant back to the project. These costs are required to be in line with eligible costs for RDA TIGER project.

A.3.4. Persons or categories of persons that may receive financial support

These grants can be given to persons or legal persons which can demonstrate the necessary capacities to provide expertise and/or support actions required by the project supported Research Data Alliance Working Groups, as documented in the WP6 approved WG Support plan for each WG. Typically, these entities are individuals, or research or repository organisations with history of working in academic or industry open science development but can also include other experts or expert organisations (legal persons) with history on development of research data, research software, other research outputs, or research evaluation related research or development. Applicants who are directly funded by RDA TIGER (i.e. consortium members) are not eligible for funding.

The Open Call is open to any applicant individual or legal entity, and communicated via the Commission Funding and Tenders platform, and widely advertised by the RDA TIGER project. Entities subject to EU restrictive measures under Article 29 of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and Article 215 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU)⁸ and entities covered by Commission Guidelines No 2013/C 205/059 are not eligible to participate in any capacity in this action.

A.3.5. Criteria for giving financial support

- 1) **Excellence:** Excellence of the proposed work, determined in reflection to the specification of the WG needs in the call text. (50% weighting)
- 2) **Implementation:** Ability of the applicant to produce the required tasks, determined by information on the past activities related to the call text (e.g. RDA, EOSC, Open Science expertise). (50% weighting)
- 3) Request for the financial amount does not exceed the amount indicated in the open call.
- 4) Formally able to receive the financial support, i.e. able to provide necessary documentation and identification to fulfil the requirements for receiving grants in the call.

Methodology: In a case of several qualifying applicants based on criteria 3) and 4), the Selection Committee will use a formal scoring system, where each Committee member will provide evaluation score from 1 (lowest) to 10 (best) for the criteria 1) Excellence and 2) Implementation. Applicants with lower arithmetic average score than 5 in either category cannot be chosen. Highest sum of average scores given for criteria 1) and 2) will be chosen for the financial support. In the case of ties, the candidate with highest average score for criteria 1) will be chosen.